

Some macroscopic observations about COVID-19 mortality in Israel

Goizalde Badiola Manuel Graña

University of the Basque Country
goizalde.badiola@ehu.eus

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Introduction

Why Israel?

- Israel has been like a testbed during the pandemic for several extreme measures
 - Strong lockdowns and social measures
 - Pioneering implementation of sanitary/vaccination pass
 - Monoculture of Pfizer Biontech vaccines until very late in the pandemic

Variables

Figure: All variables from ourworldindata.com smoothed and normalized

Cases, vaccine doses, deaths

Normalized to [0,1]

Figure: COVID-19 cases, vaccinations and deaths normalized and smoothed with a 7-days window

Stringency index, deaths

Normalized to [0,1]

Figure: Plot of Stringency index and COVID-19 deaths normalized and smoothed with a 7-day window

Vaccination doses, ICU patients

Normalized to [0,1]

Figure: Plot of COVID-19 vaccinations and ICU patients normalized and smoothed with a 7-day window

Theoretical expectation

Anticipated assumption

Figure: Theoretical expectation of the congruence between variables and how each one affects the others positively or negatively

Overall Signal Correlation

Figure: Overall Signal Correlation Matrix 2020-2022

Overall Signal Correlation

Highlights

- Non-surprising positive correlations
 - Deaths – cases, Deaths – ICU patients
- Surprising positive correlation
 - Deaths – Vaccination
- Surprising null correlation
 - Stringency index – deaths and Stringency index – cases

Cross-Correlation between deaths and cases

`xcorr(new deaths smoothed, new cases smoothed)`

Figure: tagged lags sorted by importance: [11, -356, -142, -467, 171]

Cross-Correlation between deaths and vaccinations

`xcorr(new deaths smoothed,new vaccinations smoothed)`

Figure: tagged lags sorted by importance: [3, 367, 180, -205]

Cross-Correlation between cases and vaccinations

`xcorr(new cases smoothed,new vaccinations smoothed)`

Figure: tagged lags sorted by importance: [364, 158, 15]

Cross-Correlation between ICU patients and vaccinations

`xcorr(ICU patients, new vaccinations smoothed)`

Figure: tagged lags sorted by importance: [16, 221, 374, -207]

Cross-Correlation between deaths and Stringency index

`xcorr(new deaths smoothed,stringency index)`

Figure: tagged lags sorted by importance: [8, 111, 269, 486, 657]

Cross-Correlation between cases and Stringency index

`xcorr(new cases smoothed,stringency index)`

Figure: tagged lags sorted by importance: [476, 649, 377, 302, 146]

Results from cross-correlation

Highlights

- Non-surprising
 - Cases match/predict deaths after 11 days
- Surprising
 - Stringency doses match/predict deaths after 8 days
 - Stringency doses match/predict cases after 146, 302 days
 - Vaccination doses match/predict ICU after 16 days
 - Vaccination doses match/predict deaths after 3 days
 - Vaccination doses match/predict cases after 15, 158 days, and maximal at 364 days??

Linear Regression Variable Importance

Regressing COVID-19 deaths from the other variables

Figure: Plot of Estimate value ordered by p-Value

Variables	Estimate	SE	tStat	pValue
hospitalized patients	0.8572	0.0532	16.1011	8.3387e-48
tests	-0.3850	0.0356	-10.8178	8.6695e-25
ICU patients	0.2436	0.0308	7.9146	1.4502e-14
stringency index	0.1274	0.0263	4.8457	1.6576e-06
cases	-0.1201	0.0674	-1.7835	0.0751
vaccinations	-0.0314	0.0258	-1.2159	0.2246

Table: Results of the Linear Regression Variables Importance

Observations

- Main effect comes from the hospitalized patients
- Stringency index has a positive coefficient highly significant $p \ll 0.005$
- Vaccination doses has a minor negative effect with low significance ($p=0.02$)

Linear Regression Variable Importance shifting lags from 1 to 31 days with normalized data

Figure: Plot of Estimate value ordered by p-Value

Observations

- Past values of cases and hospitalization series have a large effect
- Vaccination doses appear among the most salient variables

Random Forest Variable Importance

Regressing COVID-19 deaths from the other variables

Figure: Plot of Feature Importance values

Variables	importance
ICU patients	4.8580e-04
hospitalized patients	2.6535e-04
vaccinations	2.5479e-04
stringency index	2.5368e-04
cases	1.1591e-04
tests	6.3907e-04

Table: Results of Random Forest Variables Importance

Observations

- Stringency index and vaccine doses appear as more important variables than cases and tests
- The results do not provide the direction of causality

Observations

- Past values of stringency index appear as more important variables than cases and tests
- The results do not provide the direction of causality

Conclusions

- The relation of virus control measures (stringency + vaccination) shows some surprises that are not easy to characterize numerically
- There is no reference model of the expected response to control measures
- However, in COVID-19 after mass vaccination the peaking of omicron cases was strongly correlated stopped with the end of massive testing

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